

**DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF DEVELOPING AND USING
INSTRUCTIONAL CONTENT FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-
SUPPORTED EDUCATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES: A
CONCEPTUAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS FOR
UNIVERSITY PRACTICE**

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Annotation. This article examines the distinctive features of creating and using instructional content for artificial intelligence-supported education within university English language courses. The analysis frames content development as a methodological workflow consisting of goal-setting, constraint definition, content generation, pedagogical editing, and classroom integration. The paper highlights how artificial intelligence tools can accelerate content production, enable level-appropriate adaptation, support interdisciplinary contextualization, and expand communicative tasks such as role-plays and scenario-based speaking activities. It also discusses the strengths of traditional instructional materials—particularly their stability and structured progression—alongside their limitations in meeting rapidly changing student needs and contemporary communication formats. **Keywords:** artificial intelligence; English language teaching; instructional content development; content adaptation; communicative tasks; role-plays; interdisciplinary context; higher education; level-appropriate materials; pedagogical editing and integration.

Introduction. In recent years, generative technologies based on artificial intelligence (capabilities for creating text, images, audio and code) have begun to radically change the speed and flexibility of developing educational content in the education system, especially in foreign language teaching. Content creation for English lessons traditionally relies on a system of textbooks, teaching and methodological guides, audio-video resources and teacher-prepared handouts. However, in a university setting, the size of the audience, the difference in the level of student preparation, interdisciplinary needs (for example, terminology in medicine, engineering, economics), time constraints and curriculum requirements require frequent content updates. At this point, artificial intelligence tools become an important resource for tasks such as rapid content creation, level adaptation, development of multiple-choice exercises, creation of dialogue scenarios, simplification or complexity of the text, and precise “wrapping” of lexical and grammatical goals.

However, creating content “quickly” is not enough: the issues of linguodidactic quality of the content, its communicative purpose, its compliance with the curriculum, the balanced development of language competencies, and its integration into the real educational process of the university require constant methodological control. It is also noted in scientific sources that, although generative models are powerful, they are not completely reliable and, in some cases, can “confidently” give facts (p. 1, 2). Therefore, educational content created with the help of artificial intelligence must be processed, checked, and didactically “edited” by the teacher in terms of purpose, audience, and context.

This article provides a scientific and methodological analysis of the specific aspects of creating and using educational content for artificial intelligence education in English lessons. The focus is on content design, development process, mechanisms for use in the classroom, integration with traditional content, adaptation to the needs of university students, as well as a discussion of the useful and useless aspects of old educational content.

Literature review.

The global literature on the impact of artificial intelligence on education is developing in two main directions: (a) the possibilities and limitations of artificial intelligence technologies; (b) their pedagogical adaptation to the real learning process. UNESCO’s guidance documents on artificial intelligence and education policy, while recognizing the potential of artificial intelligence to improve education, emphasize the need for a systematic approach, local context, collaboration, and “human-technology” harmony (pp. 3, 4–5). At the same time, it is noted that the growth of the artificial intelligence market in education and the proliferation of technological solutions are also accelerating the content production ecosystem (3, p. 3). This situation makes the issue of methodological balance between “speed” and “quality” in creating content for English language lessons relevant.

In the methodology of language education, the communicative approach and the competency model remain the leading direction. The Pan-European system for determining the level of language proficiency allows for the “adaptation” of content to the needs of the time by linking types of language activity (reception, production, interaction) and strategies to lesson design, as well as highlighting modern competencies such as online interaction and mediation (2, p. 35). This methodologically justifies the fact that content created with the help of artificial intelligence should serve communicative tasks and real communication scenarios.

Empirical research on generative artificial intelligence in language learning has increased dramatically since 2023–2024; systematic reviews note that generative tools are often used in higher education, especially in the context of English, and that research designs and focuses are becoming more diverse (4; 5b). This literature also shows the most common uses in practice: creating level-appropriate text, creating dialogues, developing “stimuli” for written and spoken speech, quickly generating lexical and grammatical exercises, and preparing material close to authenticity in interdisciplinary topics (4; 5b). At the same time, technical reports clearly state that generative models have limitations such as “hallucinations” (the creation of false information with confidence) and that caution is needed in contexts where reliability is important (1, 2-p.). In language education, this can be a significant risk factor, especially in fact-rich texts (scientific-popular, historical, economic) and professional English content (terms, processes).

Thus, the literature analysis leads to the following scientific conclusion: although artificial intelligence tools are a powerful accelerator in content creation, methodological design, language level standards, and quality control remain central; otherwise, the communicative value of the content will decrease, and the likelihood of incorrect or inconsistent language units will increase (1, 2-p.; 2, 35-p.; 4; 5).

Research approach.

This article is a conceptual analysis written in a practical-methodological direction, viewing the process of creating educational content using artificial intelligence in university English lessons as a cycle of “development–adaptation–integration–improvement”. The framework consists of three layers: the first layer is the curriculum and level requirements; the second layer is the linguodidactic construction of the content (target vocabulary, grammar, functional speech acts, communication strategies); the third layer is application scenarios in group and independent learning.

The main idea of this approach is that artificial intelligence does not teach content “itself”; it is a tool that quickly translates the methodological intention designed by the teacher into the form of text, exercises, dialogues, tasks and materials. Therefore, the article focuses on content design decisions (why this type of material, what kind of speech situation, what level of complexity, what interdisciplinary context) rather than technological descriptions. In the development of communicative competence, in particular in areas such as online interaction and mediation, the need to adapt content to types of language activity is harmonized with the approaches of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (2, p. 35).

Didactic specificity of creating educational content using artificial intelligence.

The most important specificity of creating content using artificial intelligence is the transformation of content from a single “ready-made material” into the possibility of quickly adapting, reassembling and making it multi-variant. Traditional textbook content is usually repeated in the same order, with the same examples and exercises; artificial intelligence, while maintaining the same methodological goal, can develop variants, change the context, and create situations that suit the student’s interests or orientation. From a didactic point of view, this process can be explained through three mechanisms: personalization, contextualization, and rapid iteration. Personalization refers to the re-presentation of content in a complexity appropriate to the student’s language level, lexical reserve, and needs. For example, rewriting a text on the same topic with a simpler syntax, replacing synonyms, reducing repeated lexical units, or, conversely, strengthening the academic type can be quickly done by artificial intelligence. However, here the teacher must control the “level norm”: artificial intelligence sometimes loses semantic subtlety in the process of simplification or can introduce unnecessary idioms. Therefore, content creation is not seen as “automatic generation,” but as “generation + methodological editing”; This approach is consistent with technical warnings about the limited reliability of models (p. 1, 2).

Contextualization is the process of bringing language learning content closer to real-life and professional situations. In a university environment, many students want to use English not in a “general” way, but within the framework of their field of study (professional communication, presentations, short correspondence, discussions with a team). With the help of artificial intelligence, the same grammar topic can be re-contextualized in different directions: for example, the topic of “future forms” can be presented in the context of a clinical plan in medicine, project planning in business, or workflow planning in information technology. Such contextual materials enhance communicative activity and clarify the “purpose of communication”; the idea of linking language activity types and strategies to lesson design is consistent with the Common European Framework (p. 2, 35).

Rapid iteration is the ability to test and quickly update content. In traditional content, processing takes more time: finding text, adapting, creating exercises, preparing answer keys. With artificial intelligence, a teacher can prepare several parallel options for the same topic, smoothing out the level difference between groups or trying out different “role” scenarios within one lesson. However, the speed of iteration does not automatically ensure content quality control; on the contrary, as

the speed increases, the need for methodological filtering also increases (1, 2-p.; 4;5).

A practical model of the content creation process: “goal—constraint—prompt—edit—integration”.

From a practical point of view, the process of creating content using artificial intelligence for university English lessons can be organized as a five-stage workflow. Here, the concept of “prompt” is interpreted not as a technical term, but as a clear statement of the teacher’s methodological task.

The first stage is to clearly define the goal. The goal is not limited to “topic”; it should include language skills (speaking, listening comprehension, reading, writing), speech situations (student-student, student-teacher, student-client), functional units (making a proposal, refusing, asking for clarification, agreeing), and lexical-grammatical focus. This stage guarantees the communicative value of the content and distinguishes it from random generation.

The second stage is to introduce constraints. In a university setting, the constraints are usually: the language level of the students, the duration of the lesson, the sequence of topics in the curriculum, the available resources (audio, video, platform), the number of groups and the interdisciplinary profile. It is these constraints that make the content generated by AI “necessary”; otherwise, the content may be generic and far from the real purpose of the lesson. The Common European Levels of Reference and communicative approaches serve as methodological “criteria” for adapting to the language level (2, p. 35). The third stage is content generation. Here, the teacher can ask AI to create a text, dialogue, role-playing scenario, discussion questions, a short listening comprehension script, a lexical set and “speaking prompts” for speaking. The most important condition is to view the generation result as “raw material”. Since the technical reports note that the models have limited reliability and can sometimes provide incorrect information (p. 1, 2), texts rich in fact or with professional terminology must necessarily be checked. This check is interpreted not as an ethical discussion, but as a methodological-quality control: is the terminology correct, is it appropriate to the context, and does the task serve a communicative purpose?

The fourth stage is editing and didactic “packaging”. The text provided by artificial intelligence is transformed into a learning task by the teacher: a pre-task (preparation), while-task (main activity) and post-task (reinforcement) logic is created. For example, when given a dialogue text, the student first isolates the main phrases, then plays a role, and then retells it by changing the situation. At this stage,

the teacher introduces language units “without noticing” them to the student: the target grammar and lexicon are used naturally in the activity.

The fifth stage is integration. How does content “enter” the lesson: group work, pair work, homework, online forum, short speech? The fact that the European Framework distinguishes competencies such as online interaction and mediation (p. 2, 35) means that content should be organized as a communicative task not only in the classroom, but also in the digital environment. The integration stage ensures that content created with artificial intelligence does not remain “material”, but becomes an “activity”.

The specificity of using artificial intelligence content in English lessons: group, independent learning and interdisciplinary needs.

The specificity of using artificial intelligence content is primarily due to the fact that it accelerates the transition of the lesson from a “teacher-centered” model to an “activity-centered” model. The teacher can focus more on creating situations that make the student speak, without spending a lot of time explaining the same topic. In this case, AI content acts as a “trigger to start talking”: a controversial question, a problematic situation, a role-playing scenario, a short story, a news-like text, an announcement or materials in the form of an email.

The main feature when used in a group is the ability to create several parallel content paths for one topic. For example, if students at the A2 level and students at the B1 level study together in the classroom, the teacher can prepare the same situation (for example, “solving a problem in a university library”) in two different levels of complexity, but keep the final communicative result the same. This approach provides differential assistance without disrupting the “general rhythm” of the lesson.

In independent learning, AI content enhances the “micro-learning” format: a student can read one dialogue for 10–15 minutes a day and compose a short correspondence based on that dialogue, or prepare for a mini-discussion on one topic. The main feature here is the “multiple processing” of the content: the student re-enacts the same situation in different roles, in different contexts, for different purposes. This way, the language units are repeated, but the repetition does not become boring.

From the point of view of interdisciplinary needs (professional English), artificial intelligence content is especially convenient for the university: the teacher can create a text, introducing the terminology of a certain direction, but without violating the language level norm. This practice increases the “relevance” of the content, increases the motivation of the student. However, in professional content, fact and

term verification should be strong, since generative models are not always reliable (p. 1, 2). Thus, in interdisciplinary content, the teacher, along with the “methodological organizer”, also plays the role of “fact editor”.

Old educational content and new (enriched with artificial intelligence) content: useful and useless aspects.

Traditional (old) educational content is often strong in its methodological systematicity, level-appropriate sequence, authorial editing, and stable quality. Textbooks and proven manuals are the product of many years of methodological experience and usually control the growth of grammar and lexicon. In addition, traditional content serves as a “basic roadmap” for the teacher: the sequence of topics, types of exercises, repetition blocks, group management are facilitated. However, the disadvantage of old content is that it quickly becomes outdated: examples, context, communicative situations can become distant from the lives of today's students. University students often live in an environment of digital communication, online collaboration, short correspondence and quick oral presentations; if the content does not meet this need, the lesson can become more of an “exercise” than a “language”. The fact that online interaction and mediation skills are specifically covered in the European framework (2, p. 35) also means that the content should reflect modern communication formats.

The advantages of new, AI-enriched content are rapid updating, contextual adaptation and a large number of options. The teacher prepares materials for one topic in different forms: one as a dialogue, one as a story, one as an email, one as an announcement, one as a social media post. In this way, the same language goal is processed in different communicative formats and transfer is enhanced. Systematic reviews of empirical studies also show that generative tools are often used in such practical tasks (4; 5).

However, the downside of new content is the risk of “methodological overproduction”. If there is too much content but it does not connect to the logic of the curriculum, it becomes a fragmented experience for the student. The second risk is errors in factual and linguistic norms: generative models can sometimes offer incorrect information or artificial, unnatural expressions; technical reports warn about the limited reliability of the models (pp. 1, 2). Therefore, the effectiveness of AI content directly depends on the methodological filter and quality of the teacher’s editing.

The most optimal strategy is to create an “adaptive layer” with AI content, keeping traditional content as a “skeleton”. That is, the progression of the textbook and the

main objectives are maintained, but examples, dialogues, situations and additional exercises are adapted to the context of the lesson using artificial intelligence. This approach provides a didactic balance between stability (traditional systems) and flexibility (artificial intelligence).

The role of the teacher and content authorship: a shift from “creator” to “editor”

As artificial intelligence facilitates content creation, the role of the teacher shifts from “author who writes everything by hand” to “designer of the learning experience”. This shift is visible in three aspects.

First, the teacher learns to clearly articulate the methodological intention. The more methodologically precise the task given to the artificial intelligence, the more the result will be in line with the learning objective. This process strengthens the teacher’s lesson design competence: he or she clearly expresses the language purpose, the situation, the constraints on the role and the expected outcome from the student.

Second, the teacher strengthens the competence of editing and adaptation. Checking the generative text, adjusting it to the level, removing unnecessary complexity, reducing non-communicative sentences, and increasing targeted phrases — all of these reinforce the teacher’s role as a “content editor.” The caveats that the model has limited reliability and may sometimes provide inaccurate information (pp. 1, 2) make this role a methodological necessity.

Third, the teacher must be a master of integration. It is not the content itself, but the activities carried out with the content that develop the student's language skills. Therefore, the teacher connects the content to formats such as pairs, groups, role-playing, discussion, short speeches, online correspondence. The inclusion of competencies such as online interaction and mediation in the Common European Framework (2, p. 35) makes the issue of integration even more important: the content should serve not only text, but also digital communication experience.

Practical application scenario for the first year of university: A2–B1 level groups.

At the first university stage (A2–B1), students often have a grammatical foundation, but problems with “speed”, “confidence” and “sustained speech” are observed in speaking. Therefore, content creation using artificial intelligence is effective if it relies on three types of materials that support speaking: (a) short dialogues and role-playing; (b) problem situations and discussion questions; (c) interdisciplinary mini-contexts (close to professional life).

For example, on the topic of “campus life”, 8–10 replica dialogues are created for level A2, and 12–16 replica dialogues for level B1; in both cases, the target functions are the same: greeting, stating a problem, clarifying, suggesting a solution, expressing gratitude. The teacher edits the dialogue, increasing the target phrases in each replica and reducing unnecessary synonyms. Then the situation in the role-play is changed: instead of the library, “registration office”, “student dormitory”, “laboratory” are introduced, but the speech functions are preserved. This allows the content to be adapted, reassembled, and made multiple-choice.

At the next stage, students are given “discussion cards”: each card contains a small situation and two or three questions. Artificial intelligence quickly creates these cards, and the teacher checks them for level compliance. In this process, the topic of the old textbook is preserved, but the situations are brought closer to the student's life. As a result, the systematicity of the traditional content is preserved and the flexibility of the new content is added.

For interdisciplinary mini-contexts, for example, the topic of "health and lifestyle" can be presented in the form of a simple clinical interview for medical students, and in the form of a discussion of "healthy budget for students" for economics. If fact-rich segments (for example, statistics) are included, the teacher will definitely check, because the generative model can provide incorrect information (1, 2-p.). Thus, the practical scenario shows the development of flexible content along with methodological control.

Discussion: conditions for systematic implementation and sustainability factors.

Several organizational and methodological conditions are important at the institute and course levels for the sustainable use of artificial intelligence content. The first is compliance with the curriculum and textbook progression. If each teacher reproduces the content separately, in his own way, the general standards of the course may be fragmented. Therefore, it is advisable to agree on “content design rules” (level, topic, speech functions, minimum and maximum size) within the course.

Second, the transformation of the quality control and editing process into a routine practice. This is not a matter of ethics or evaluation, but of scientific and methodological hygiene: naturalness of the text, suitability of target expressions, fact-checking, clarity of the communicative task. The fact that technical sources clearly indicate the limitations of the models (p. 1, 2) reinforces the fact that quality control is “necessary” rather than “optional”.

Third, updating the methodological competence of the teacher. UNESCO-oriented educational policy documents emphasize the need for systematic preparation and interaction with practice as technology and artificial intelligence enter the education system (p. 3, 4–5). In this context, the teacher should learn not "using artificial intelligence", but "methodological design using artificial intelligence". That is, didactics, not technology, remains at the center.

The uniqueness of creating and using AI-based learning content in English lessons is that the content development process is accelerated, flexible, and the options are increased depending on the context. This provides a practical advantage in university settings, especially in the first years of A2–B1 level, in increasing the number of communicative situations focused on speaking, meeting interdisciplinary needs, and organizing the lesson in an activity-centered manner (4; 5). At the same time, scientific and technical warnings that generative models are not completely reliable and can in some cases “confidently” provide incorrect information (p. 1, 2) make teacher editing and methodological filtering a prerequisite. The most optimal result is observed when the systematicity and stable quality of traditional content are combined with the flexibility of artificial intelligence content: the textbook progression remains the “basic skeleton”, while artificial intelligence enriches the lesson with “layers of activity” appropriate to the local context, student interests and professional needs. The coverage of communicative activities, strategies, online interaction and mediation directions in the Pan-European Language Learning System (2, p. 35) methodologically substantiates the need for content created with the help of artificial intelligence to serve realistic communication scenarios, digital communication formats and functional speech goals. As a result, artificial intelligence content is interpreted not as a “finished product”, but as a didactic resource that serves to quickly and flexibly build an educational experience designed by the teacher.

Artificial intelligence tools significantly accelerate the process of developing educational content, facilitate the adaptation of content to the needs and language levels of students, and allow the creation of multiple-variant materials that serve the same methodological goal. As a result, the teacher is not completely dependent on textbooks and manuals, but can more freely approach the development and improvement of content that is relevant to the real situation of the audience, while maintaining the requirements of the curriculum. This is especially relevant at the first-year university stage (levels A2–B1), and gives practical results in getting students to speak, increasing communicative situations, covering interdisciplinary topics in simplified English, and smoothing out differences in the levels of different groups. However, making content created with the help of artificial intelligence

effective is not limited to “quick creation”. In order for the content to be didactically valuable, it must be inextricably linked to the learning objective, communicative tasks of the lesson, language level, and sequence of topics in the university program. In this sense, artificial intelligence content should often be viewed not as a “finished final product”, but as “raw material” that can be methodically processed, edited, and adapted to the lesson activity. Since generative models can sometimes suggest unnatural expressions or make errors in fact-based texts (p. 1, 2), the process of checking, adapting and didactic “packaging” content becomes an integral part of the teacher’s work. Therefore, it is not the creation of content itself, but the transformation of content into real tasks and activities in the lesson (role-playing, discussion, dialogue-based exercises, interdisciplinary mini-conversations) that is the main factor determining the effectiveness of education. The main advantage of traditional content is its systematicity, stability, level-appropriate progression and methodological balance. However, its disadvantage is its rapid obsolescence, lack of full compliance with modern communication formats, and its remoteness from the life and professional context of students. New content enriched with artificial intelligence, on the contrary, is useful for its flexibility, rapid updating of the context and a large number of options; however, if it increases without methodological control, it can reduce the coherence of the learning process and cause excessive fragmentation. Therefore, the most optimal approach is to maintain traditional content as a “basic skeleton” and create an “adaptive additional layer” through artificial intelligence. That is, the main topics, competencies, and lesson logic are based on the curriculum, and artificial intelligence brings them to life through realistic communicative scenarios that are appropriate to the student's needs and situation. This process also changes the role of the teacher: the teacher appears not only as a content author, but also as a content author and editor. He clearly defines the methodological goal, introduces restrictions (level, time, topic), receives options with the help of artificial intelligence, and then processes them to fit the lesson activity. As a result, the teacher can reduce the time spent on explanations in the lesson and devote more time to engaging the student in dialogue, developing strategies for continuing speech, and strengthening speaking and writing skills on interdisciplinary topics. The coverage of communicative activities, strategies, online interaction and mediation competencies within the framework of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (2, p. 35) also means this: content in today's education should serve the tasks of real and digital communication, not just grammatical exercises.

As a final result, the following general scientific conclusion can be drawn: the effectiveness of creating educational content for AI education in English lessons

depends on the harmony of three factors - methodological design appropriate to the curriculum, the creation of flexible and multi-variant content using AI, and the teacher's ability to transform the content into real learning activities through editing and integration. When this harmony is ensured, AI content becomes a learning resource that is focused on speaking in a university environment, relevant to the context, quickly updated and adapted to the needs of the student; otherwise, it can remain just a collection of duplicate materials.

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